

CURRENT STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL THINKING IN FUTURE ECONOMISTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880542>

Abstract. *The article discusses the development of economic acumen and economic responsibility through the development of analytical thinking in future economists, the fact that rational thinking is the main element of the image of a modern economist, and the mechanisms of educating future economists on the basis of creative approaches in modern higher education. information is provided*

Keywords: *self-control, analytical thinking, education, integration, economy, market economy, pedagogy, comprehensive approach, modern science and technology, independent thought, specialist training system.*

Creating knowledge, skills, and abilities related to the development of analytical thinking. Effective use of international models of economic education is gaining urgent importance in order to reform the system of training economists in the higher education system of our country at the level of modern requirements. Because in developed and market economy countries of the world, the training of economists who can adapt to the sudden changes of the new mechanism and compete in any conditions has already been done to the modern economic education system.

Today, in contrast to the past, education of new independent thinking and creative students remains one of our main problems. "Indeed, during the student years, young people reach the stage of biological maturity, and from a social point of view, maturity and physical maturity. In students, important aspects of intelligence, such as self-control, self-evaluation, self-awareness, and self-management, rise to a new high level of development.

General professional, social, economic and specialized sciences play an important role in the development of students' thinking and the formation of a scientific worldview.

Such qualities, skills and abilities that develop analytical thinking are very important for a future economist to become a competitive specialist. Without these qualifications and skills, strong leaders and economic experts cannot be trained. Such qualities are also highly valued by employers of countries with strong economies. Given the growing importance of these qualities today, it becomes clear how analytical thinking can be of practical benefit to future economists.

Students' thinking mainly "develops rapidly and continuously during study, practical training and independent learning activities. Sometimes the lecture process requires reproductive thinking from them, but practical exercises, independent assignments, laboratory assignments require productive (creative) thinking. Both forms of education are realized with the help of students' mental work, goal-oriented and coordinated attention. In the course of education, the theoretical, practical and methodological foundations of modern economy, deep theoretical methodological, scientific and methodical knowledge of entrepreneurship and business laws are mastered. Especially in this period, thinking acts as an effective intelligence tool for the student."

It is also important to develop creativity and critical thinking in future economists based on analytical thinking. Creative thinking means solving an economic problem in a fundamentally new way. The task of critical thinking in this process involves evaluating existing procedures and

values in the economic sphere. This provides an opportunity for future economists to solve economic issues quickly and easily, and provide prompt service based on analytical thinking. Creative thinking, formed on the basis of logic, directs future economists to create new ideas, and critical thinking identifies their shortcomings and shortcomings. Although used separately, both modes of thinking are necessary for creative tasks, so critical thinking can often be a hindrance or a hindrance to creative thinking. Creative thinking requires future economists to give full freedom to their thoughts and direct them to a specific field.

In the process of economic education, the pedagogue fulfills the task of teaching, creating knowledge, skills, and future economists experience the process of mastering. It is a complex pedagogical and psychological process, involving intuition, perception, imagination, thinking. Learning is the process of forming the acquisition, cognitive skills, thinking operations and actions of future economists.

It should be noted that the integrated various educational-scientific production associations are not only necessary during the stable development of the economy and society, but also that during the transition period, in the process of reforming the society, economy, and the education system, the training of personnel in this field is extremely necessary.

One of the factors that develop the analytical thinking of future economists is logical observation and quick analysis of the situation. This imposes the obligation of economic higher education institutions and HEIs to introduce new directions, approaches and principles of education in the field of economics. One of the important tasks of higher education is the training of competent and competitive personnel who meet the requirements of the labor market. Foreign experience shows that logic, which is one of the philosophical sciences, plays an important role in the development of the analytical thinking of future economists, along with the transition of economic sciences on the basis of new methodologies and approaches. It is clear that the main priority task is to educate future economists as owners of new thinking and deep intelligence. In Uzbekistan, there is a need to establish a pedagogical process based on the cooperation of specialized sciences and social and humanitarian sciences, and to develop pedagogical technologies based on specific cases, in the formation of the analytical thinking necessary for them in training future economists and in training the personnel of the economic sector.

The reserve of qualified personnel prepared in the current period does not meet the requirement of readiness for modern economic situations and economic problems formed on the basis of them. Such a situation, in turn, requires higher educational institutions to implement innovations in the personnel training system and labor market relations. The lack of analytical thinking of today's economists is estimated by their inability to adapt to the situation, being limited only by theoretical knowledge, not being able to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, and not having a broad outlook and deep thinking. The content of the reforms carried out in our society requires the training of future economists and the qualification of economic personnel, the availability of opportunities for them to solve non-standard problems, regular improvement of their professional skills, and readiness for social changes.

In the context of globalization, a number of contradictions appear in the educational space. This is related to the demands placed on the modern specialist by the society aimed at humanizing the educational environment, which are more clearly manifested in the following: a) increasing requirements for the quality of knowledge and skills of future specialists, low level of development of analytical thinking of modern students; b) development of analytical thinking with the need to

acquire fundamental professional knowledge and the current practice of teaching in an educational institution without being directed to a specific goal; v) insufficient use of the available opportunities for the development of students' worldview and analytical thinking with the level of knowledge in the field of specialization.

Today, in order to ensure that future economists have their place in the labor market, it is necessary to develop the skills of social experience in them. That's why there is a need to reform the educational process and create new pedagogical methods of training highly analytical thinking personnel who can show their personality, abandoning the old system of teaching and taking exams. In this process, future economists need to develop logical analytical skills, information, reality, problem analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction thinking. In this regard, it should be noted that the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" has an important practical, theoretical, and historical significance. In this document, the task of fundamental reform of higher education, fundamental improvement of the system of training of qualified specialists in accordance with the country's development strategy, organization of training of modern bachelors and masters on the basis of international requirements is set. Higher education is a factor that determines the future development of the country and plays a decisive role in reforming all aspects of civil society. That is why the training of highly qualified personnel, competitive in the labor market, the fundamental improvement of the quality and efficiency of the higher education system is the main basis of the social policy of every country. When students' worldview and way of thinking change, when they switch to a new way of thinking, then their analytical thinking is manifested at a high level.

In the conditions of the deepening and improvement of market economy relations, the main task is to form future economists with high professional training, loyalty to their profession, adaptability to changing social life, regularly improving their knowledge in an independent state, being able to give suggestions and recommendations at a constant pace, and independent analysis of their activities. It should be noted that the quality of the higher education process is closely related to the process of training highly qualified specialists.

Curriculum for training highly qualified personnel and specific pedagogical features of developing analytical thinking. The content of the curriculum for training highly qualified personnel in higher educational institutions specializing in the training of personnel in the economic field consists of two parts: ensuring that future economists acquire professional knowledge and develop their analytical thinking, forming the personal, ethical, and business characteristics necessary for a modern specialist. Therefore, it is one of the important tasks to increase the possibilities of educating specialists from the higher education institutions of our country who can influence the economic, political and social processes of the world, and to change the approaches in this regard.

Peculiar pedagogical features of developing analytical thinking in future economists are as follows:

- a comprehensive approach to the education of future economists, formation of socio-philosophical knowledge in them along with specialized subjects, organization of the educational process based on the latest pedagogical technologies;

- to create a scientific environment that develops the analytical thinking of future economists as a deep and critical thinker, who can stand in a creative, objective position;

- in the pedagogical process, introducing an innovative methodology for developing logical thinking and analytical thinking, which is very useful in the professional activity of future economists;

- it is necessary to inculcate in future economists the skills of working with people individually and in a team, adaptability to the times and social environment, to give special knowledge about the ability to solve problems on the spot, to form these characteristics;

- in the training of future economists, it is necessary to improve their economic knowledge, as well as to develop the skills of solving economic problems and making the right decisions;

- developing a methodology for working with practical "cases" in the training of future economists, not limited to theoretical knowledge.

In the current development of higher education, theoretically based, goal-oriented, practically applicable pedagogical innovations occupy an important place. Pedagogical innovation is not a new technique and technology, but a new way of thinking and a new attitude to the lesson. Pedagogical innovations at the current stage of development of our country have a direct impact on all aspects of higher education. Such methods that develop logical thinking and analytical thinking are very necessary for today's education. It should be noted that innovations help to introduce the achievements of human intelligence to the socio-economic aspects, the types of services provided expand, and their quality improves.

The development of modern science and technology has an impact not only on the production process, but also on the education system. In particular, improving the education system and bringing it to the level of world standards is becoming an urgent and important issue today. Therefore, the role of independent activity in the development of free thinking and critical vision in future economists is incomparable. For example, analytical thinking in future economists prepares the ground for the formation of thinking qualities such as independence, firmness in thoughts, criticality, analytical approach.

The consistent development of economic thinking comes from the inextricable connection between theory and practice. It is the achievement of an integral connection between economic theory and economic policy that has a positive effect on the rise of economic culture. "Development of national economic thinking requires recognition of private ownership, ensuring fundamental structural changes in national economic sectors, increasing the importance of small business and private entrepreneurs, as well as mastering knowledge of specialists capable of international competitiveness. In the current conditions, the formation of a new economic mindset among young people plays an important role. Because economic thinking is the basis for society members to learn to think independently and make decisions according to the situation. Economic thinking is the result of economic thinking, knowledge. Economic thinking is expressed in feeling the limit, knowing the norm, making a decision by comparing the desire with the real possibility through calculation.

At the current stage of economic development, education completely changes its place in social life and becomes the main factor of economic development. The high socio-economic importance of education appears as a basis for the formation of human capital. In today's economy, not other production resources, but human capital is recognized as the basis of competitiveness and efficiency of social production. The transformation of knowledge into the main social capital, the growth of knowledge, which can be seen from the acquisition of knowledge, is determined by the fact that the person who consumes this product, the whole society and specific enterprises will

benefit from it. From all this, the basis for mixed financing of education and the development of market relations in this field emerges.

The economic importance of education for future economists is determined by its great role in raising the social and cultural level of the population, developing the country's production forces, and increasing the efficiency of social work. The field of vocational education is directly related to the process of reproduction of social products. It plays a very important role in creating a skilled labor force for all sectors of the economy. From this point of view, the work of education workers is one of the types of social work.

"The level of competitiveness of economic systems depends on a large number of factors, such as: the availability of resources, the attraction of investments in technology and the quality of the business environment. In particular, competitiveness in the short term is determined by the structural structure of the economy, as well as the nature and efficiency of institutions, the quality and breadth of the infrastructure, and other factors that affect the efficiency of the national system. Competitiveness depends to a large extent on the state's ability to create an economic and legal environment that supports the stable process of production.

Special attention is paid to increasing the effectiveness of continuous education through the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the teaching of economic subjects. Pedagogical technologies are educational tools that provide an opportunity to develop and improve the personal qualities of students with the help of teaching and the use of modern information technologies, and it has a unique didactic and methodological basis.

Also, the main basis of modern pedagogical technology depends on the selected technologies for the cooperation of the teacher and the student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal. Every educational technology used in the educational process to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal can establish cooperation between the teacher and the student and achieve a positive result. .

In order to improve the quality and efficiency of economic studies for future economists, it is recommended to use pedagogical technologies in three types of training based on the possibilities of modern information technologies, taking into account the specific characteristics of lecture, practical and laboratory training. . "Economics materials are divided into thematic blocks taking into account the number of study hours, 2-8 study hours are allocated to each lecture, and the content and volume of practical and laboratory exercises corresponding to this thematic block are determined. In this method, the internal consistency and integrity of learning each subject is fully preserved, and students have the opportunity to develop skills and competencies related to the subject more fully and more purposefully.

The main goal of economic education for future economists is to raise their economic literacy, economic consciousness, and economic culture. This is a system of theoretical knowledge, as well as a set of economic knowledge, skills and abilities, which directly affects the student's economic consciousness, as a means of personal development.

In conclusion, the main task of higher education is to open and develop individual opportunities of the student, to help open and grow personal freedom and creativity. Today, the struggle of two opposing directions: fundamentalization and professionalization is important in the training of highly educated specialists. Acquired fundamental knowledge can help in practical activities only when it reaches a certain level of professionalization. And, on the contrary, if the fundamental training is not sufficient, the process of professionalization cannot show its

effectiveness. Currently, there are objective criteria for fundamentalization: the nature of forming a system of relations with other disciplines; systematic, generalized, holistic nature of scientific knowledge; the existence of a system of laws on the possibility of qualitatively and quantitatively predicting the beginning, course and development of events, events, processes; it is measured by the breadth of the scope of covering the entire life activity of a person with laws. These criteria consist of interrelated factors. Therefore, in preparing future economists for their professional activities, it is necessary to form the nature of independence and freedom in them.

REFERENCES

1. Nazarova, G. A. (2022). Will be on the basis of modern economic education Principles of pedagogical development of analytical thinking in economists. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 9579-9585.
2. Назарова, Г. А. (2022). Аналитик тафаккурни ривожлантиришнинг педагогик зарурати. *Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal*, 3(3), 309-314.
3. Nazarova, G. (2021). Modern pedagogical factors for the development of analytical thinking in future economists. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 511-517.
4. Алимжонова, Г. И. Қ., & Назарова, Г. А. (2022). Аналитик тафаккурни ривожлантиришнинг педагогик зарурати. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 187-196.
5. Gribincea, A., Amar, R., & Burlachenko, D. (2020). Creativity as a factor of innovative sustainable economic development. In *World economy and international economic relations* (Vol. 3, pp. 67-71).
6. Назарова, Г. А. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК ИҚТИСОДЧИЛАРДА АНАЛИТИК ТАФАККУРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ВОСИТАЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(В3), 457-464.
7. Алимжонова, Г. И. Қ., & Назарова, Г. А. (2022). ТЕХНОЭТИК МАДАНИЯТ ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ МАЗМУН-МОҲИЯТИ, УНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 181-186.
8. Mirzamahmudova, N., Maxmudova, N., & Nazarova, G. (2021). МАТЕМАТИК MASALALARNI YECHISHDAGI BA'ZI BIR MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI HAL QILISHDA MANTIQUIY FIKRLASHNING AHAMIYATI. *Scientific progress*, 2(7), 746-749.
9. Alimjonova, G. (2021). Modern competencies in the techno-culture of future technical specialists. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(06), 78-84.
10. Alimjonova, G. (2021). Modern competencies in the techno-culture of future technical specialists. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(06), 78-84.
11. Alimjonova, G. (2021). Modern competencies in the techno-culture of future technical specialists. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(06), 78-84.
12. Каримов, Ш. Т., & Хожиакбарова, Г. (2017). АНАЛОГ ЗАДАЧИ ГУРСА ДЛЯ ОДНОГО НЕКЛАССИЧЕСКОГО УРАВНЕНИЯ ТРЕТЬЕГО ПОРЯДКА С СИНГУЛЯРНЫМ КОЭФФИЦИЕНТОМ. *TURIN POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY IN TASHKENT*, 121.

13. Alimjonova, G. (2021). The need for integration of social and technical knowledge in the development of technological culture of students of higher technical educational institutions. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 502-510.
14. Қизи, Г. А. И. (2022). ТЕХНОЭТИК МАДАНИЯТ ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ МАЗМУН-МОҲИЯТИ, УНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРАТИ. *INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 3(3), 329-333.
15. Mahkamova, D. (2022). Fazoda Optimal Kvadratur Formula Xatolik Funkionali Normasi. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 13, 199-206.
16. Rasulov, R. ., Sattorov, A. ., & Mahkamova, D. T. . (2022). View of the Derivative Quadrature Formula Norm in Space . *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 10, 70–75.
17. Расулов, Р., Сатторов, А., & Махкамова, Д. (2022). Вычисление Квадрат Нормы Функционала Погрешности Улучшенных Квадратурных Формул В Пространстве. *Central asian journal of mathematical theory and computer sciences*, 3(4), 114-122.
18. Shavkatjon o'g'li, T. B. (2022). SOME INTEGRAL EQUATIONS FOR A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(4), 160-163.
19. Shavkatjon o'g'li, T. B. (2022). Proving The Inequalities Using a Definite Integral and Series. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 13, 64-68.
20. Tillabayev, B. (2022). EQUATION OF THE DERIVATIVE OF THE FUNCTION TO SOLVE EQUATIONS. *Science and innovation*, 1(A7), 717-720.
21. qizi Tillabayeva, G. I. (2020). No Local Conditional Problems for The Simple Differential Equation of the First Order Linear. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(1), 3-6.
22. qizi Tillabayeva, G. I. (2020). Problem of Bisadze-Samariskiy for A Simple Differential Equation of the First Order Linear That the Right Side Is Unknown and The Coefficient Is Interrupted. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(2), 20-26.
23. qizi Tillabayeva, G. I. (2019). Problems for A Simple Differential Equation of the First Order Linear That the Right Side Is Unknown and The Coefficient Is Interrupted. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(12), 10-14.